

An absorption spectral study for the interaction of praseodymium(III) ion with dimethylglyoxime in absence and presence of calcium(II) and zinc(II) ions in aqueous and aquated organic solvents

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Abstract : The absorption spectra of Pr^{III} with dimethylglyoxime (Hdmg) in absence and presence of Ca^{II} and Zn^{II} have been studied in aqueous and aquated organic solvents (i.e. CH₃OH, DMF, CH₃CN and C₄H₈O₂) in equimolar mixtures. The variation in energy parameters like Slater-Condon (F_k), Lande spin-orbit coupling constant (ξ_{sp}), Racah (E^k), Nephelauxetic ratio (β), bonding parameter ($b^{1/2}$) and percent covalency (δ) have been calculated. The agreement between the observed and calculated values of energy is depicted. The observed oscillator strengths for the transition of ³H₄ ground state to the excited multiplet have been discussed. The Judd-Ofelt intensity parameters T_λ ($\lambda = 2, 4, 6$) for all the complexes were evaluated by applying the Judd-Ofelt theorem to the observed oscillator strengths. The values of the intensity parameters are compared and discussed to investigate the sensitivity of the intensity parameters to the ligand environment.

Keywords : Absorption spectra, hypersensitive, pseudo-hypersensitive, Nephelauxetic effect, dimethylglyoxime (Hdmg).

Introduction

Pr^{III} ion shows a characteristics 4f-4f absorption spectra which correspond to transition from the ³H₄ ground state to the ³P₂, ³P₁, ³P₀ and ¹D₂ states. According to electric dipole moment principle, these transitions are forbidden but are partially allowed by the induced electric dipole moment. Judd¹ and Ofelt² made significant theoretical expressions for the oscillator strength of the induced electric dipole moment, taking account of the mixing between the 4f orbitals and other orbitals. Paramagnetic Pr^{III} ion can be utilized as an absorption spectral probe in biological reactions and it provides an opportunity in using Pr^{III} 4f-4f transition spectra in studying several biochemical reactions involving Ca^{II}. Recently, David^{3,4}, Sumitra⁵ and their coworkers had discussed the complexation of Pr^{III}, Nd^{III} with glutathione reduced in presence and absence of Zn^{II} in aquated organic solvents and the complexation of Pr^{III}, Nd^{III} with π -electron density of butene-1,4 and butyne-1,4-diols in non-aqueous solutions have also been reported by an absorption spectral analysis. Furthermore, the complexation of Nd^{III} with adenosine in presence and absence of Zn^{II} in aquated organic solvents have been reported

by Kriyananda⁶.

In this paper, we report the results of detailed study of the absorption spectra of Pr^{III} with dimethylglyoxime (Hdmg) in absence and presence of Ca^{II} and Zn^{II} ions in aqueous and aquated organic solvent mixtures (aquated DMF; 50%, v/v). The values of energy parameters and intensity parameters have been determined.

Experimental

Dimethylglyoxime (99.0% purity, Himedia), praseodymium(III) nitrate hexahydrate (99.0% purity, Central Drug House (P.) Ltd., New Delhi), calcium nitrate-4-hydrate (98% purity, E. Merck) and zinc nitrate-6-hydrate (98% purity, E. Merck) have been used for spectral analysis. The solvents used in the study are CH₃OH, DMF, CH₃CN and C₄H₈O₂ (1,4-dioxan), which are of AR grade from E. Merck. The sample solutions of Pr^{III}; Pr^{III} : Hdmg; Pr^{III} : Hdmg : Ca^{II} and Pr^{III} : Hdmg : Zn^{II} are prepared in concentration of 10⁻² M in different solvents (50%, v/v). All the spectra are recorded on temperature controlled (by using water circulating HAAKE DC thermostat) Perkin-Elmer-Lambda-35 UV-Visible spectrophotometer in the range 350–910 nm at 298 K.

Results and discussion

The transition ${}^3H_4 \rightarrow {}^3F_2$ (occurring at 5200 cm^{-1}) of Pr^{III} which satisfies selection rules $\Delta S = 0$, $|\Delta L|$ and $|\Delta J| \leq 2$, depends on $U^{(2)}$ matrix elements and show substantial changes even minor changes in the coordination environment. Such transition is called hypersensitive transition and is not generally studied in solution spectral analysis. But it is not so in the case of the transitions ${}^3H_4 \rightarrow {}^3P_2, {}^3P_1, {}^3P_0$ and 1D_2 of Pr^{III} . These transitions are regarded as the 'Ligand Mediated Pseudo-hypersensitivity' or 'pseudo-hypersensitive transitions'^{7,8}. The shape, energy and oscillator strengths of hypersensitive and pseudo-hypersensitive transitions can be interrelated with coordination number according to Karraker⁹.

We observed that the intensification of the spectral bands is highest in aquated DMF and DMF containing as one of the equimolar solvent mixtures due to greater ligating strength of DMF as compared to other solvents and hence we have only been emphasized in aquated DMF. The comparative absorption spectra is shown in Fig. 1 of Pr^{III} ; $\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} : \text{Hdmg}$; $\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} : \text{Hdmg} : \text{Ca}^{\text{II}}$ and $\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} : \text{Hdmg} : \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$ in aquated DMF. These bands showed an appreciable red-shift with respect to corresponding free-ion on

complexation, but the intensity of the $4f-4f$ bands increased significantly when the Hdmg, Ca^{II} and Zn^{II} salts are added to the free ions, which clearly demonstrates the stimulating effect of Ca^{II} and Zn^{II} towards the complexation of Pr^{III} with Hdmg.

The energy of $4f-4f$ transitions consists of two major components : Columbic (represented by Slater-Condon, F_k) and spin-orbit interaction (represented by Lande, ξ_{4f}) between $4f$ electrons, while f^k and A_{so} are the angular components of spin-orbit columbic interaction as given by the following relation,

$$E = f^k F_k + A_{so} \xi_{4f} \quad (1)$$

We use the observed band energies as E_{obs} and the zero point energies (E_{0i}) and partial derivatives of Pr^{III} ion given by Wong^{10,11}, the correction factors ΔE^k and $\Delta \xi_{4f}$ have been calculated by the least-squares fit method. The calculated correction factors are then added to the zero-order parameters to obtain the Racah parameters (E^k) and the spin-orbit interaction parameter (ξ_{4f}). The Slater integrals (F^k) have been evaluated from Racah parameters using relevant expressions. The rms deviations between the energies (E_{cal}) calculated using these parameters and the observed energies (E_{obs}) are within experimental limits.

Fig. 1. Comparative absorption spectra for (a) Pr^{III} ; (b) $\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} : \text{Hdmg}$ (1 : 1); (c) $\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} : \text{Hdmg} : \text{Ca}^{\text{II}}$ (1 : 1 : 1) and (d) $\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} : \text{Hdmg} : \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$ (1 : 1 : 1) in aquated DMF.

The values of Nephelauxetic ratio (β)¹²⁻¹⁵, bonding parameter ($b^{1/2}$) and percent covalency (δ) are determined by using the following relations to study the types of bonding with the metal and ligand.

$$\beta = \frac{F_k^c}{F_k^f} \text{ or } \frac{E_c^k}{E_f^k} \quad (2)$$

$$b^{1/2} = \left[\frac{1 - \beta}{2} \right]^{1/2} \text{ and} \quad (3)$$

$$\delta = \left[\frac{1 - \beta}{\beta} \right] \times 100 \quad (4)$$

These values are presented in Table 1. There is decrease in the value of the Slater-Condon (F_k), Racah (E^k) and Lande spin-orbit coupling constant (ξ_{4f}) which suggests that the complexation led to increase in the values of percent covalency (δ) as compared to the corresponding

parameters of the free ion. This is in corroboration with the expansion of the central metal ion orbital when the ligand is added to metal ion. Further, value of Nephelauxetic ratio (β) (0.9447-0.9455) in this system is less than unity and the values of bonding parameter ($b^{1/2}$) (0.1651-0.1663) are positive which indicates that the complexes are covalent in nature.

The experimental value of oscillator strength (P_{obs}) of absorption band given by Gaussian Curve Analysis¹⁶ is

$$P_{\text{obs}} = 4.6 \times 10^{-9} \times \epsilon_{\text{max}} \times \Delta\bar{\nu}_{1/2} \quad (5)$$

where, $\Delta\bar{\nu}_{1/2}$ = half-band width and ϵ_{max} = molar extinction coefficient corresponding to energy $\bar{\nu}$ in wave number.

Other parameters like Judd-Ofelt intensity parameters T_λ ($\lambda = 2, 4, 6$) have also been computed from the Judd-Ofelt expression by using the partial and multiple regression method. These parameters have been used for the determination of the calculated values of oscillator strengths (P_{cal}) and these values are presented in Table 2. The

Table 1. Computed values of energy interaction parameters i.e. Slater-Condon, F_k (cm^{-1}), Lande spin-orbit coupling, ξ_{4f} (cm^{-1}), Racah, E^k (cm^{-1}), Nephelauxetic ratio (β) and bonding parameter ($b^{1/2}$) and covalency parameters (δ) of Pr^{III} ; Pr^{III} : Hdmg (1 : 1); Pr^{III} : Hdmg : Ca^{II} (1 : 1 : 1) and Pr^{III} : Hdmg : Zn^{II} (1 : 1 : 1) in aquated organic solvents ($\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{DMF}$; 50 : 50, v/v)

Parameters	Pr^{III}	Pr^{III} : Hdmg	Pr^{III} : Hdmg : Ca^{II}	Pr^{III} : Hdmg : Zn^{II}
F_2	309.0503	308.9720	308.9657	308.9594
F_4	42.6644	42.6536	42.6527	42.6519
F_6	4.6667	4.6654	4.6654	4.6653
ξ_{4f}	720.7922	719.8295	719.8267	719.8238
E^1	3509.1584	3508.2696	3508.1980	3508.1264
E^2	23.7471	23.7406	23.7406	23.7401
E^3	614.4127	614.2445	614.2445	614.2320
β	0.9455	0.9447	0.9447	0.9447
$b^{1/2}$	0.1651	0.1663	0.1663	0.1663
δ	5.7678	5.8544	5.8556	5.8569

Table 2. Computed and observed values of oscillator strengths ($P \times 10^6$) and Judd-Ofelt parameters ($T_\lambda \times 10^{10}$) for Pr^{III} ; Pr^{III} : Hdmg (1 : 1); Pr^{III} : Hdmg : Ca^{II} (1 : 1 : 1) and Pr^{III} : Hdmg : Zn^{II} (1 : 1 : 1) in aquated organic solvents ($\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{DMF}$; 50 : 50, v/v)

System	${}^3H_4 \rightarrow {}^3P_2$	${}^3H_4 \rightarrow {}^3P_1$	${}^3H_4 \rightarrow {}^3P_0$	${}^3H_4 \rightarrow {}^1D_2$	T_2	T_4	T_6
$\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{DMF}$	$P_{\text{obs}} (P_{\text{cal}})$	$P_{\text{obs}} (P_{\text{cal}})$	$P_{\text{obs}} (P_{\text{cal}})$	$P_{\text{obs}} (P_{\text{cal}})$			
Pr^{III}	4.3795 (4.3795)	1.2135 (0.9674)	0.7106 (0.9531)	0.9890 (0.9890)	-66.21	2.6587	13.665
Pr^{III} : Hdmg	4.3947 (4.3947)	1.2157 (0.9686)	0.7108 (0.9543)	0.9907 (0.9907)	-66.45	2.6621	13.714
Pr^{III} : Hdmg : Ca^{II}	4.4042 (4.4042)	1.2196 (0.9707)	0.7111 (0.9563)	0.9914 (0.9914)	-66.92	2.6679	13.744
Pr^{III} : Hdmg : Zn^{II}	4.4067 (4.4067)	1.2197 (0.9740)	0.7175 (0.9596)	0.9954 (0.9954)	-66.19	2.6770	13.750

Judd-Ofelt intensity parameters T_4 and T_6 values are greater than zero and supported to the applicability of Judd-Ofelt theory of $4f-4f$ transitions for Pr^{III} complexes. Clearly, one can find that the T_6 is much more sensitive to the coordination environment than the T_4 but T_2 occasionally showed negative values, which is physically unacceptable. Though a very good agreement is obtained between the observed and calculated values of oscillator strength levels for ${}^3H_4 \rightarrow {}^3P_2$ and 1D_2 , differences to a large extent occur between the corresponding values of ${}^3H_4 \rightarrow {}^3P_1$ and 3P_0 levels. The complexation and covalency have been found to be related to spectral intensity (i.e. oscillator strength). The values of oscillator strengths of the complexes are found to be higher as compared to free ion which shows higher complexation and covalency. Hence, it may be concluded that higher magnitude of oscillator strength we observed indicates inner sphere complexation.

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